

Mechanical Properties of 3D Printed Porous Ti-6Al-4V Alloy for Biomedical Applications – Manufacturing Technology Journal – 2025

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Optimising the mechanical properties required for biomedical applications is something that porous Ti-6Al-4V structures offer the opportunity to do. Triply periodic minimal surface (TPMS) structures, such as the Diamond and Gyroid structures, provide interconnected pores that can be used to adjust strength, stiffness and deformation. The mechanical behaviour of these two architectures under compressive and bending loads is compared in this study, with the use of additively manufactured samples. The results demonstrate that pore geometry significantly impacts mechanical behaviour. Diamond structures exhibit higher stiffness and strength, whereas Gyroid structures provide a more isotropic and flexible response. These findings emphasise the importance of architecture when designing implants and other components for which optimised mechanical properties and geometry are essential.

Keywords: Diamond, Gyroid, Ti-6Al-4V, Porous Structures, TPMS

1 Introduction

Titanium and its alloys, particularly Ti-6Al-4V, are widely used in biomedical engineering thanks to their combination of strength, low density, corrosion resistance and biocompatibility [1–6]. However, despite these favourable properties, solid implants often cause stress shielding due to a mismatch in stiffness between the implant and the surrounding bone. Introducing porosity into the structure can reduce the effective modulus, enhance osseointegration and permit tissue ingrowth, thereby improving implant performance [7–11].

Among the various porous designs, triply periodic minimal surface (TPMS) structures, such as Diamond and Gyroid, are of particular interest. These geometries offer a highly regular, interconnected network of struts and pores that can be adjusted to control mechanical properties, energy absorption and cell adhesion. Diamond structures typically provide higher stiffness and strength, while gyroid structures offer improved flexibility and a more isotropic mechanical response. This makes both architectures promising for biomedical implants [11–14].

This study focuses on the mechanical comparison of Diamond and Gyroid porous Ti-6Al-4V structures produced by additive manufacturing. The aim is to shed light on how pore architecture influences compressive and flexural behaviour, providing guidance for designing implants that more closely mimic the mechanical environment of human bone.

2 Experiment details

Porous Ti-6Al-4V scaffolds featuring triply periodic minimal surface (TPMS) geometries — specifically Diamond and Gyroid — were fabricated for the purpose of studying their mechanical performance. The samples were designed using CAD software and generated with MSLattice to ensure interconnected pore networks and a target porosity of 70%, see **Fig. 1**. Elementary unit cells and larger assembled structures were printed on a thin, non-porous substrate to provide structural support during the additive manufacturing process.

Additive manufacturing was performed using a ConceptLaser M2 Cusing LPBF printer fitted with a 200 W Yb:YAG fibre laser, in an atmosphere containing less than 0.5% O₂. The layer thickness was 30 μm, the scanning spacing was 80 μm, and the scanning speed varied between 800 and 1250 mm s⁻¹ depending on the study. Both the Diamond and Gyroid structures were printed vertically and subsequently evaluated in as-built and post-processed conditions.

The Ti-6Al-4V powder was gas-atomised and spherical, characterised by a particle size distribution of d10 ≈ 23 μm, d50 ≈ 33 μm and d90 ≈ 48 μm. Gravimetric measurements confirmed that the experimental porosity

closely matched the designed value of 70% (approximately 69% for the Diamond structure and 67% for the Gyroid structure), with minor deviations attributed to partial melting or powder adhesion.

Fig. 1 Porous gyroid and diamond structures: (a) - elementary cell gyroid (G), (b) - elementary cell diamond (D), (c) samples with diamond and gyroid structures in their initial state after printing – SEM

The Vickers hardness and compressive strength of Diamond and Gyroid porous Ti-6Al-4V structures were evaluated. Hardness measurements were taken from the surface and cross-section of both materials, while compression tests were carried out on each porous material using a LabTest 5.250SP1-VM universal testing machine at room temperature. The compression properties were evaluated at a constant loading rate of 5 mm/min.

3 Result and discussion

3.1 Microstructure

The Diamond and Gyroid TPMS structures differ in both geometry and the angle and thickness of the individual struts, which has a significant effect on their mechanical performance. In this study, the average strut diameter was approximately 0.3 mm for the Diamond structure and 0.2 mm for the Gyroid structure, see **Fig. 2**. Previous studies have shown that deviations from the CAD design occur during manufacturing: horizontal struts tend to be thicker, with discrepancies of up to 198 μm for gyroid and up to 105 μm for diamond. Meanwhile, vertical struts remain closer to the designed thickness [15, 16]. This implies that the effective strut thickness depends heavily on build orientation, influencing both stiffness and strength. Furthermore, comparative studies suggest that Diamond structures generally demonstrate greater compressive stiffness and strength than Gyroid structures, primarily due to the distinct distribution of stress and load-bearing capacity within the unit cell [17, 18].

The LPBF-processed Ti-6Al-4V exhibits a predominantly martensitic α' microstructure, which is typical for rapid cooling rates inherent to this technique [19, 20]. Both D and G structures display visible micro-pores inside the struts, acting as potential stress concentrators. The martensitic morphology is expected to provide high strength but limited ductility. Future HIP treatment would transform this into an equilibrium $\alpha+\beta$ structure, improving toughness and fatigue resistance [19].

Fig. 2 SEM images of diamond (D) and gyroid (G) structures after LPBF fabrication: (a, b) show the diamond lattice at different magnifications, and (c, d) show the gyroid lattice at different magnifications. In both cases, martensitic microstructure with visible pores is observed within the lattice struts.

3.2 Hardness

Vickers hardness tests (HV0.5) revealed comparable values for both porous topologies, reaching 395 ± 18 HV0.5 for the Diamond and 415 ± 14 HV0.5 for the Gyroid. These values slightly exceed the hardness measured for bulk Ti-6Al-4V in the as-built state (353 ± 11 HV1), indicating the strengthening effect of the fine martensitic structure [19]. The results confirm that despite the high porosity, the local material properties of **the struts** remain close to, or even above, those of bulk LPBF-produced Ti-6Al-4V.

3.3 Compressive and bending properties

Compression tests revealed clear differences between the two TPMS topologies, see **Fig. 3**. The Diamond (D) structure achieved a compressive yield strength (CYS) of 81 MPa, whereas the Gyroid (G) structure exhibited a significantly higher value of 162 MPa. Both lattices exhibited an initial linear-elastic behaviour, followed by non-linear deformation due to the progressive collapse of the porous structure.

The superior performance of the gyroid can be explained by its continuous surface architecture and finer structure (with finer struts at 0.2 mm compared to 0.3 mm in the D structure), which allows for a more uniform distribution of stress and prevents localised failure. Similar trends have been reported in the literature, where gyroid scaffolds often display a higher yield strength at comparable porosities due to their smooth stress distribution and reduced stress concentrations [21, 22]. However, other studies have noted that the diamond lattice can exceed the gyroid lattice when designed with thicker struts or lower porosity, highlighting the importance of relative density and manufacturing precision [23–25].

The measured CYS values typically fall within the wide range reported for porous Ti-6Al-4V scaffolds, which is usually between ~ 50 and 200 MPa, depending on the geometry and porosity [26–28]. Significantly, the gyroid structure in this study approaches the upper limit of this range, indicating its suitability for use in biomedical implants, where a balance must be found between strength and high porosity to enable bone ingrowth and minimise stress shielding [29, 30].

Three-point bending tests further emphasised the structural differences between the D and G lattices. As Fig. 3 shows, the Diamond lattice exhibited higher bending stress (up to ~260 MPa) than the Gyroid lattice (~180 MPa), despite having a lower compressive strength. This behaviour may be attributed to the thicker (0.3 mm) struts in the Diamond lattice, which offer greater resistance to bending loads. The Ti-6Al-4V implant is a promising material for biomedical applications because it has low stiffness and high porosity [31]. Porous Ti-6Al-4V ELI reduces stiffness to 80 GPa and increases cell proliferation. In comparison to the study of Li X. et al. [32] (maximum bending strength of 126.3 MPa), both porous structures demonstrated higher initial bending strength values.

Fractographic analysis using a scanning electron microscope (see Fig. 4) revealed distinct failure modes for the two structures. In the diamond lattice, the fracture surfaces exhibited a combination of brittle cleavage and ductile dimples, which were frequently initiated at pores or adhered powder particles. By contrast, the gyroid exhibited smoother fracture surfaces, reflecting more uniform stress pathways, but also a tendency towards localised collapse once critical deformation was reached.

As a research study discovered [33], the main distinctions between these structures also lie in their failure mechanisms. The diamond lattice is prone to abrupt failure due to the sudden buckling of struts, while the gyroid lattice demonstrates a more gradual failure through the steady collapse of its curved walls. Therefore, the type of printed structure chosen has a significant influence on its mechanical behaviour and overall performance. Even though a thorough mechanistic analysis lies beyond the scope of this study, the observations underscore the paramount necessity to adapt post-processing strategies, such as HIP, to the geometry and loading conditions of printed scaffolds.

Fig. 3 The mechanical properties of the Ti-6Al-4V alloy are shown in the form of compressive stress-strain diagrams and bending stress-strain curves for the porous samples.

Fig. 4 Fracture surfaces of LPBF-fabricated porous structures with diamond and gyroid geometries in their as-printed states: *D_(AP)*: diamond structure in as-printed state; *G_(AP)*: gyroid structure in as-printed state.

4 Conclusion

Both Ti-6Al-4V Diamond and Gyroid lattice designs are popular for biomedical implants and engineering applications. However, they differ in terms of mechanical behaviour, manufacturability and biological performance.

- 1) The LPBF-fabricated Diamond and Gyroid TPMS structures exhibited a martensitic microstructure containing micro-pores within the lattice struts.
- 2) The hardness values of the porous structures were comparable to or higher than those of the bulk material, indicating preserved local strength.
- 3) Compression tests showed that the Gyroid structure had significantly higher strength, while the Diamond structure performed better under bending.
- 4) The structural design (e.g. strut thickness and topology) plays a decisive role in determining the mechanical response, underlining the need for application-specific optimisation.

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